

1 *For Science of The Total Environment*

2 Title

3 **Substantial uptake of nitrous oxide (N₂O) by shoots of mature European beech**

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5 Katerina Machacova^{a*}, Thomas Schindler^{a,b}, Laëtitia Bréchet^c, Ülo Mander^{a,b} and Thorsten E.
6 E. Grams^d

7 *^aDepartment of Ecosystem Trace Gas Exchange, Global Change Research Institute of the
8 Czech Academy of Sciences, Belidla 4a, CZ-60300 Brno, Czech Republic*

9 *^bDepartment of Geography, Institute of Ecology & Earth Sciences, University of Tartu, 46
10 Vanemuise, EST-51014 Tartu, Estonia*

11 *^cINRAE, UMR EcoFoG, CNRS, Cirad, AgroParisTech, Université des Antilles, Université de
12 Guyane, FR-97310 Kourou, France*

13 *^dDepartment of Life Science Systems, School of Life Sciences, Technical University of Munich,
14 Von-Carlowitz-Platz 2, DE-85354 Freising, Germany*

15 **email: machacova.k@czechglobe.cz, telephone: +420 703 828 755*

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17

18 **Abstract**

19 Similar to soils, tree stems emit and consume nitrous oxide (N₂O) from the atmosphere.
20 Although tree leaves dominate tree surface area, they have been completely excluded from field
21 N₂O flux measurements and therefore their role in forest N₂O exchange remains unknown. We
22 explored the contribution of leaf fluxes to forest N₂O exchange. We determined the N₂O
23 exchange of mature European beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) stems and shoots (i.e., terminal
24 branches) and of adjacent forest floor, in a typical temperate upland forest in Germany. The
25 beech stems, and particularly the shoots, acted as net N₂O sinks ($-0.254 \pm 0.827 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2}$
26 stem area h⁻¹ and $-4.54 \pm 1.53 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2}$ leaf area h⁻¹, respectively), while the forest floor
27 was a net source ($2.41 \pm 1.08 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2}$ soil area h⁻¹). The unstudied tree shoots were
28 identified as a significant contributor to the net ecosystem N₂O exchange. Moreover, we
29 revealed for the first time that tree leaves act as substantial N₂O sinks. Although this is the first
30 study of its kind, it is of global importance for the proper design of future flux studies in forest
31 ecosystems worldwide. Our results demonstrate that excluding tree leaves from forest N₂O flux
32 measurements can lead to misinterpretation of tree and forest N₂O exchange, and thus global
33 forest greenhouse gas flux inventories.

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37 **Key words:** exchange, *Fagus sylvatica*, forest floor, greenhouse gas, tree leaves, tree stem.

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40 **1. Introduction**

41 Temperate forests, predominantly found in Europe and North and Central America, cover an
42 area of approximately 630 million ha (in 2010), representing 16% of the world's forested area
43 (FAO, 2017). In general, temperate forest ecosystems are considered to be a substantial natural
44 source of nitrous oxide (N₂O) (1.6 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) and an important carbon dioxide (CO₂) sink (–
45 340 kg ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) (Dalal & Allen, 2008), with N₂O having a global warming potential 298 times
46 that of CO₂ (Myhre *et al.*, 2013).

47 Nitrous oxide is produced naturally in soils as a facultative by-product from a wide range of
48 microbiological nitrogen (N) turnover processes, including mainly aerobic nitrification and
49 anoxic denitrification processes, which can be closely interconnected. The denitrification
50 processes are the only processes reducing N₂O to N₂ and therefore consuming N₂O under
51 anaerobic conditions. At the soil surface, N₂O can be exchanged with the atmosphere by gas
52 diffusion (depending on the balance between N₂O production and consumption processes) and
53 by advection driven by air pressure gradients (Smith *et al.*, 2003). Plants, including woody
54 plants, can also contribute to ecosystem N₂O exchange by taking up soil-produced N₂O and
55 transporting it to the atmosphere via roots, stems, and/or leaves (Rusch & Rennenberg, 1998;
56 Machacova *et al.*, 2016, 2019). Furthermore, plants can produce N₂O directly in plant tissues
57 (Smart & Bloom, 2001; Hakata *et al.*, 2003), consume N₂O from the atmosphere by a non-
58 specified mechanism (Machacova *et al.*, 2017b, 2021a), and alter N turnover processes in
59 adjacent soil (Yu & Chen, 2009). Cryptogamic stem covers (*i.e.*, *photoautotrophic organisms*
60 *living on tree bark*) can further contribute to N₂O exchange of trees through their ability to emit
61 and consume N₂O (Lenhart *et al.*, 2015; Machacova *et al.*, 2017b, 2021a). Due to the still very
62 limited studies on N₂O fluxes of mature woody plants grown under their natural field
63 conditions, the contribution of these individual processes to the total net N₂O exchange is
64 unknown.

65 European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) is a native and widely grown tree species typical for
66 upland forests of Central and Southeast Europe. It covers approximately 15 million ha in Europe
67 (Brunet *et al.*, 2010). Soils of beech forests are regarded as sources of N₂O (Papen &
68 Butterbach-Bahl, 1999; Pihlatie *et al.*, 2005b; Brumme & Borcken, 2009; Wen *et al.*, 2017). In
69 addition to soils, a very limited number of studies show that beech trees might even exchange
70 N₂O with the atmosphere and therefore contribute to the N₂O exchange of beech forests.
71 Relevant N₂O emissions were found, however, only from beech seedlings and young and
72 mature beech trees predominantly under artificial conditions of high N fertilisation or flooding
73 (Pihlatie *et al.*, 2005a; Machacova *et al.*, 2013; Díaz-Pinés *et al.*, 2016), which resulted in
74 increased soil N₂O production and thus increased availability of N₂O for plant-mediated
75 transport to the atmosphere. Under natural field conditions, N₂O emissions from mature beech
76 stems appear to be low or even below the detection limit even as soils have been identified as
77 N₂O emitters (Díaz-Pinés *et al.*, 2016; Wen *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, a recent study found a
78 consistent uptake of N₂O from the atmosphere by mature beech stems grown under natural field
79 conditions with soils consuming N₂O (Machacova *et al.*, 2017b). Determination of N₂O uptake
80 potential by tree stems is a new finding and has recently been proven for several tropical tree
81 species grown under low soil N₂O fluxes (Bréchet *et al.*, 2021; Machacova *et al.*, 2021a; Daniel
82 *et al.*, 2023).

83 Tree surface area consists not only of the stem surface area, however, but is in fact dominated
84 by leaf area. To our knowledge, tree leaves have been completely excluded from the field N₂O
85 flux measurements worldwide. A single study on N₂O fluxes from shoots (i.e., *terminal*
86 *branches with leaves, petioles, and short shoot stems in top tree crowns*) of mature trees (*Pinus*
87 *sylvestris*) performed under natural field conditions clearly identified tree shoots as significant
88 emitters of N₂O to the atmosphere, with shoot N₂O emission rates exceeding stem emission
89 rates by a factor of 16 (Machacova *et al.*, 2016). To accurately evaluate the contribution of

90 widely grown European beech trees to forest N₂O exchange and budgets, it is crucial to include
91 measurements at the level of beech leaves in study designs.

92 The aim of our study was to quantify N₂O exchange from both the stems and leaves of
93 European beech trees, which is the first time that leaf N₂O exchange has been measured under
94 natural field conditions. We investigated the unknown role of beech leaves in N₂O exchange
95 with the atmosphere and estimated the flux contribution of beech leaves to tree and forest
96 ecosystem N₂O exchange. Fluxes of N₂O from stems and shoots of mature trees were
97 determined in a typical temperate upland forest in Germany during June 2019. The
98 measurements were accompanied by parallel determinations of stem and shoot CO₂ exchange
99 (as an indicator of tree physiological activity) and forest floor N₂O and CO₂ fluxes, as well as
100 numerous additional environmental parameters.

101

102 **2. Materials and Methods**

103 **2.1. Site description and study design**

104 The measurements were performed at the Kranzberger Forest experimental station near
105 Freising, Germany (48°25'12"N; 11°39'42"E; 490 m a.s.l.). The site is dominated by mixed
106 forest with European beech (ca 90 years old, tree density of 352 trees ha⁻¹) and Norway spruce
107 (*Picea abies* L. Karst, ca 70 years old, 301 trees ha⁻¹), growing on nutrient-rich luvisol with
108 high water holding capacity (Pretzsch *et al.*, 2014; Rötzer *et al.*, 2017). The N₂O fluxes were
109 studied at a beech-dominated plot within the forest. The mean tree height and stem diameter at
110 breast height (DBH) of beech trees were 26.1 and 0.29 m, respectively (Rötzer *et al.*, 2017).
111 The mean annual precipitation and temperature (1971–2000) are 750–800 mm and 7.8 °C,
112 respectively (Pretzsch *et al.*, 2014).

113 N₂O fluxes were measured at stems and shoots of three mature beech trees of average height
114 and stem diameter ($n = 3$) and at adjacent forest floor level ($n = 3$), using non-steady-state
115 chamber systems and a system of scaffolding towers present at the experimental station. The
116 towers allowed limited but technically required access to the top crowns of the selected three
117 mature beech trees. The N₂O flux determination was accompanied by simultaneous
118 measurement of CO₂ fluxes for all aforementioned forest compartments. The stem fluxes were
119 investigated in vertical stem profiles of each tree (ca 0.2, 0.9, and 1.8 m above ground). The
120 shoot fluxes were determined in top crowns at two to three positions per tree, including sun and
121 shade branches. Additionally, concentrations of N₂O and CO₂ were determined in vertical soil
122 profile (10, 20, 30, and 40 cm) close to each soil chamber position to investigate production
123 and consumption of N₂O in the soil profile. The gas flux measurements were accompanied by
124 parallel determination of soil volumetric water content (VWC) in vertical soil profile down to
125 40 cm depth and of soil temperature at 0.1 m depth. Both parameters were measured close to
126 each soil chamber position.

127 The stem, shoot, and forest floor N₂O and CO₂ fluxes at all positions and heights and all
128 ancillary parameters were measured in June 2019, with four measurement sets spread over the
129 month for stem fluxes and ancillary soil parameters, and five measurements sets for soil and
130 shoot fluxes.

131

132 **2.2. Stem flux measurements**

133 The fluxes of N₂O from tree stems were measured manually using static stem chamber systems
134 (Supporting Information Fig. S1; Machacova *et al.*, 2015, 2017b), consisting of rectangular,
135 transparent plastic containers with removable airtight lids (Lock & Lock, Seoul, South Korea)
136 and a neoprene sealing frame. They were gas-tightly affixed to the bark surface 8 days before
137 the first measurements were performed and left open all the time except measurement periods.

138 Stem fluxes of N₂O were measured in the lower part of the stems (ca 0.2 m above ground) using
139 three large chambers (internal volume of 0.0021 m³ and enclosed stem area of 0.0183 m² per
140 chamber) randomly installed to representatively cover the stem circumferential surface area.
141 Fluxes at 0.9 and 1.8 m stem height were investigated using three smaller chambers (internal
142 volume of 0.0009 m³ and enclosed stem area of 0.0084 m² per chamber) installed randomly at
143 each additional stem height. The gas-tightness of all the chambers was regularly tested by
144 application of CO₂ as a tracer gas (Machacova *et al.*, 2023). Closing lids were applied only
145 during measurements.

146 The chambers at one stem height were connected to a single flow-through system using
147 polyurethane tubing (Supporting Information Fig. S1). For measurements, the chambers at one
148 height were sealed with the lids and connected to a portable greenhouse gas analyser for N₂O
149 flux measurements. The system was operated as a closed-loop system, constantly circulating
150 the air from the chambers to the analyser and back to the chambers. For more details regarding
151 the gas flux measurements and analyses, please, see “2.6. Gas analyses”.

152

153 **2.3. Shoot flux measurements**

154 The fluxes of N₂O from tree shoots were determined manually using static shoot chamber
155 systems (Supporting Information Fig. S1). The cylindrical shoot chambers (internal volume of
156 0.0072 m³ per chamber, enclosed projected leaf area of 0.0281–0.0735 m², depending on the
157 size of the enclosed terminal branch) made from polymethyl methacrylate consisted of
158 transparent lids and removable transparent airtight chamber hats cylindrical in shape (0.25 m
159 length, 0.19 m diameter). A total of seven lids were firmly fixed to the scaffolding towers in
160 the upper canopy of three beech trees (two to three lids per tree, including both sun and shade
161 branches). The lids were attached to the top end of the branches several days before the first
162 measurements without damaging the plant tissues, and the connection was checked optically

163 for tightness before each flux measurement. For the individual measurements, the chamber hat
164 was connected to the lid with a rubber seal, enclosing the studied terminal branch inside the
165 chamber for several minutes. The chamber was connected to a portable greenhouse gas analyser
166 for N₂O flux measurements, thus creating a closed flow-through system constantly circulating
167 the same air between the chamber and the analyser. For more details regarding the gas flux
168 measurements and analyses, please, see “2.6. Gas analyses”.

169 The air temperature inside the shoot chambers was continuously monitored during the
170 chamber measurements (DT 612 thermometer, CEM, Shenzhen, China). Closed ice packs were
171 inserted to prevent excessive overheating. The rising humidity and possible water condensation
172 in the closed chambers was prevented by silica gel. The air inside the chambers was mixed
173 using small fans. Photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) was measured in parallel with the
174 shoot flux measurements using an LI-189 Quantum/Radiometer/Photometer and a
175 Q16291Quantum sensor (Li-Cor, Lincoln, Nebraska, USA). PAR values are only indicative
176 due to the manual nature of the light measurements (several single point measurements per
177 chamber closure, mean values used). Due to constantly changing external light conditions, these
178 averages give a rough estimate of the PAR conditions exposed to the shoots and cannot be used
179 for precise regression analyses with shoot N₂O fluxes (shoot CO₂ fluxes are used instead, as
180 explained below).

181

182 **2.4. Forest floor flux measurements**

183 The forest floor fluxes of N₂O were measured in the close vicinity of each studied tree
184 (Supporting Information Fig. S1). The manual dark cylindrical soil chambers used (enclosing
185 soil area of 0.0696 m², with internal volume of 0.0061–0.0071 m³ depending on the buried soil
186 depth) consisted of a polyvinyl chloride collar that had been installed in the soil several days
187 before the first gas flux measurements and a chamber hood made of a gas-tight stopper of a
188 sewer pipe (Machacova *et al.*, 2023). During the measurements, the soil chambers were closed
189 by the chamber hoods, which were gas-tightly connected to the collar using a rubber seal. To
190 analyse the N₂O fluxes, the chamber was connected to a portable greenhouse gas analyser (see
191 “2.6. Gas analyses”, Supporting Information Fig. S1). The temperature of the headspace air was
192 recorded during the measurements. The air inside the chambers was mixed with small fans. The
193 outer surface of the chamber hoods was covered by silver foil to reduce solar induced heating
194 of the chamber. All the chambers were left open between measurements.

195

196 **2.5. N₂O concentrations measurements in soil vertical profile**

197 Soil gas concentrations were determined at four soil depths (10, 20, 30, and 40 cm) near each
198 soil chamber (ca 0.5 m distant) to investigate the production and consumption of N₂O in the
199 soil profile. Four open-ended stainless-steel pipes (0.8 cm inner diameter) of lengths 20, 30, 40,
200 and 50 cm were installed in boreholes that had been drilled into the vertical soil profiles. The
201 four pipes were placed next to each other in one row ca 10 cm apart. The pipes ended 10 cm
202 above the soil in a three-way valve, which was closed between the measurements to ensure
203 equilibration of the air in the pipes with the soil air (Machacova *et al.*, 2023). Gas samples were
204 taken through the three-way valve into pre-evacuated gas-tight 12 ml glass vials (Labco
205 Exetainer, Labco, United Kingdom) in parallel with the forest floor N₂O flux measurements,

206 stored in refrigerator until analysis, then analysed in the laboratory using a gas chromatograph
207 (see “2.6. Gas analyses”).

208

209 **2.6. Gas analyses**

210 The exchange of N₂O by tree stems and shoots and by the forest floor was analysed using a
211 portable Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy gas analyser (DX-4015, Gasmeter
212 Technologies Oy, Vantaa, Finland; Warlo *et al.*, 2018) equipped with an official greenhouse
213 gas application (GAS-APP-006 spectral library) to detect water vapour, CO₂, methane, N₂O,
214 ammonia, and carbon monoxide. The application had been extended to measure also nitrogen
215 monoxide and nitrogen dioxide. All gases were explicitly manufacturer-calibrated for our
216 analyser. Every morning before the measurement campaign, the analyser was zero-point
217 calibrated with nitrogen (N₂, 99.9992% purity) to ensure accurate measurements. The quality
218 of the measured N₂O concentrations was continuously monitored during the real-time
219 measurements by evaluating the residual values and graphs for each spectra measurement
220 (Gasmeter, 2015). The quality checks revealed no significant instrumental biases in N₂O
221 concentration measurements caused by potential interference from volatile organic compounds,
222 potentially emitted from tree stems and shoots (Machacova *et al.*, 2021b). For an example of
223 the quality checks, please see Supporting Information Note S1. Moreover, intercomparison
224 measurements of N₂O fluxes from mature beech stems using an FTIR analyser (DX-4040, same
225 settings as the DX-4015 analyser used in this study; Gasmeter Technologies Oy, Finland) and a
226 gas chromatography analyser (GC; Tracera, Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan) were in close
227 agreement and showed no significant discrepancy between these detection techniques for the
228 stem N₂O uptake (Machacova *et al.*, 2021b).

229 Single measurements lasted ca 30 min for stem fluxes and ca 15 min for forest floor fluxes,
230 depending on their N₂O flux rates. The measurement time for the shoots was 2–5 min,

231 depending on CO₂ consumption and emission rate. To reduce stress-induced plant reactions,
232 the sampling threshold of shoot fluxes was set at an internal air CO₂ concentration of 300 μmol
233 CO₂ mol⁻¹ for light incubation and 500 μmol CO₂ mol⁻¹ for dark incubation. The scan frequency
234 of the spectrometer was 10 Hz. The internal pump (0.002 m³ min⁻¹) of the analyser provided
235 air mixing within the chamber systems.

236 Gas samples from the soil gas concentration sampling pipes were analysed for N₂O
237 concentrations using the Tracera GC equipped with a barrier discharge ionisation detector
238 (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan; for settings see Machacova *et al.*, 2017b). Gas samples were
239 automatically injected using a GX-271 autosampler (Gilson, Middleton, Wisconsin, USA). The
240 N₂O concentrations were calculated based on a four-concentration calibration curve (0.29, 0.43,
241 0.56, 0.70 μmol N₂O mol⁻¹). LabSolutions software (Shimadzu, Japan) was used to control the
242 chromatograph system and analyse the data.

243

244 **2.7. Flux calculation**

245 The exchange of N₂O from stems, shoots, and forest floor was calculated by linear least square
246 fits of N₂O concentrations time series in the chamber headspace as described in Machacova *et*
247 *al.* (2016). Fluxes were expressed per m² of stem, leaf, and forest floor surface area,
248 respectively. The projected leaf area of shoots enclosed in the shoot chambers was determined
249 by applying a destructive method at the end of the measurement campaign using a regular 2D
250 camera and ImageJ (vers. 1.52a, National Institutes of Health, Bethesda Maryland, USA). A
251 decrease in gas concentration over time indicated gas uptake (i.e., negative flux) and an increase
252 in gas concentration indicated gas emission (i.e., positive flux).

253 Fluxes from tree stems and shoots and from the forest floor were further roughly scaled up to
254 the ecosystem level (per-hectare values) based on tree and forest characteristics (mean DBH of
255 0.29 m, mean tree height of 26.1 m, tree density of 352 trees ha⁻¹, beech stem basal area of 22.9

256 $\text{m}^2 \text{ha}^{-1}$; Rötzer *et al.*, 2017). The upscaling procedure is described in Machacova *et al.* (2016,
257 2023). Stem surface area (11.9 m^2 per tree) was calculated as the lateral surface area of a right
258 circular cone using DBH and tree height. The stem fluxes measured at each stem height were
259 extrapolated for the entire stem height and the final trace gas flux of the total tree stem area of
260 each individual tree was calculated as a mean from these three fluxes. The beech leaf area index
261 (LAI) of $5.50 \text{ m}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}$ (Häberle *et al.*, 2012) was used for shoot flux calculations. Flux estimation
262 at the beech-dominated forest plot level is associated with uncertainties arising from both the
263 upscaling procedure itself (Machacova *et al.*, 2016) and the limitations of the new study (such
264 as large spatio-temporal flux variability versus small sampling size, daytime measurements in
265 the summer period only).

266 In this article, all flux rates expressed per m^2 are related to forest floor, stem, or leaf surface
267 area. The leaf, stem or soil area are specified in the unit only when necessary. The upscaled flux
268 rates are expressed per unit ground area (per-hectare values).

269

270 **2.8. Ancillary measurements**

271 The CO_2 exchange of tree stems and shoots and the forest floor was measured simultaneously
272 with the N_2O exchange using the same chamber systems, methods, and the portable FTIR
273 analyser as described for the N_2O exchange. Similarly, CO_2 concentrations in vertical soil
274 profiles were measured as described for N_2O concentrations (using a calibration curve of 400,
275 667, 933, and $1200 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$). The exchange of CO_2 was used as an indicator of
276 physiological activity in regression analyses with N_2O fluxes and also for classification of shoot
277 N_2O fluxes (see 3. Results).

278 Soil temperature and soil VWC were measured in the vicinity of each soil chamber in parallel
279 with the determination of forest floor gas fluxes. Soil temperature was measured at 10 cm depth
280 using a Testo 925 thermometer (Testo SE & Co., Lenzkirch, Germany). Soil VWC was

281 determined at four depths (10, 20, 30, and 40 cm) using a PR2 Profile Probe and HH2 Moisture
282 Meter (AT Delta-T Devices, Cambridge, UK).

283

284 **2.9. Statistics**

285 The flux data were tested for normal distribution (Shapiro–Wilk test) and equality of variances
286 in the different subpopulations, resulting in identification of the data as non-normally
287 distributed. Therefore, the non-parametric Mann–Whitney rank-sum test (for comparison of
288 shoot fluxes determined under high and low shoot CO₂ uptake) and Kruskal-Wallis one-way
289 analysis of variance on ranks for multiple comparisons (for comparison of forest floor, stem,
290 and shoot fluxes) were applied. Relationships between N₂O and CO₂ exchange of shoots were
291 tested with simple linear regression models. The exact tests used and *n*-values for statistical
292 analyses are given in the figure legends and in the text under “2.1. Site description and study
293 design”. Statistical significance was defined as $p < 0.05$ for all tests. Statistics were calculated
294 using SigmaPlot 11.0 (Systat Software, San Jose, CA, USA).

295

296 **3. Results**

297 **3.1. Soil parameters**

298 Soil N₂O concentrations adjacent to soil chambers 2 and 3 were similar and well below ambient
299 N₂O concentrations (Table 1). In contrast, the soil near soil chamber 1 was a hot spot for N₂O
300 and exhibited high N₂O concentrations reaching up to 3.85 ppm N₂O at 40 cm soil depth. Soil
301 CO₂ concentrations showed a rising trend with increasing soil depth, similar for all three
302 locations (Table 1). Mean soil VWC values were rather uniform across all locations during the
303 study period and ranged between 0.18 and 0.36 m³ m⁻³ at the various depths (Table 1). The
304 mean soil temperature at 10 cm soil depth was 14.7 ± 0.16 °C (mean ± standard error (SE)).

305

306 **3.2. Carbon dioxide exchange in the stems and shoots of beech trees and in the forest floor**

307 The measured net CO₂ exchange is considered only as an indicator of physiological activity,
308 helping to understand the N₂O exchange in the soil–tree–atmosphere continuum.

309 Tree stems emitted CO₂ to the atmosphere ($204 \pm 25 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ stem area h}^{-1}$; i.e., 1.29 ± 0.16
310 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; mean \pm SE; Supporting Information Fig. S2a). Stem CO₂ efflux was least in the
311 lower part of the stems and increased within the first meter of the stem (Supporting Information
312 Fig. S3). Shoot CO₂ exchange was dependent on PAR conditions ($R^2 = 0.500$, $p < 0.001$). Mean
313 shoot CO₂ emission detected under dark conditions was $68 \pm 9.8 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ leaf area h}^{-1}$ (i.e.,
314 $0.428 \pm 0.062 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and shoot CO₂ uptake under light conditions reached up to -411
315 $\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{ leaf area h}^{-1}$ (i.e., $-2.60 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). The forest floor emitted CO₂ at a rate of $533 \pm$
316 $43 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ soil area h}^{-1}$ (i.e., $3.37 \pm 0.27 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

317

318 **3.3. Nitrous oxide exchange in the stems and shoots of beech trees and in the forest floor**

319 The studied beech stems were predominantly low sinks of N₂O from the atmosphere ($-0.254 \pm$
320 $0.827 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ stem area h}^{-1}$, mean \pm SE; Fig. 1a). Study of the vertical profile of the stem
321 N₂O exchange revealed the lower stem segments (0.2 m above ground) to be weak N₂O emitters
322 ($1.60 \pm 0.75 \mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$, median $0.52 \mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$) but that the stems became uniform sinks for
323 N₂O within the first meter above ground (Fig. 2). Stem N₂O flux was not related to stem CO₂
324 efflux ($R^2 = 0.0164$, $p = 0.457$).

325 The shoots of mature beech trees under natural field conditions were found to constitute a clear
326 and strong sink of N₂O from the atmosphere, consuming $-4.54 \pm 1.53 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ leaf area h}^{-1}$
327 (Fig. 1a). Regression analysis revealed a weak relationship with the simultaneously measured
328 shoot CO₂ exchange ($R^2 = 0.145$, $p = 0.05$). The shoot N₂O fluxes were divided into two groups

329 according to the photosynthetic activity of the shoots (high versus low activity, threshold set at
330 $-100 \text{ mg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$). This simple grouping showed a significantly higher shoot N_2O uptake
331 ($-5.93 \pm 2.03 \text{ } \mu\text{g m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$) under high photosynthetic activity (i.e., high shoot CO_2 uptake
332 ranging from -120 to $-411 \text{ mg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$) compared to lower N_2O uptake (-0.905 ± 0.678
333 $\mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$) detected under low photosynthetic activity (i.e., under low shoot CO_2 uptake
334 or emission ranging from -94 to $+88 \text{ mg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$; Supporting Information Fig. S4).

335 The forest floor was a dominant source of N_2O to the atmosphere ($2.41 \pm 1.08 \text{ } \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2}$
336 soil area h^{-1} , Fig. 1a). The fluxes were not significantly related to CO_2 emissions from the forest
337 floor ($R^2 = 0.124$, $p = 0.199$).

338 To compare the N_2O exchange “capacity” of beech shoots with beech stems and forest floor
339 (i.e., measured exchange rates per m^2 of leaf, stem or soil area are not comparable), the
340 measured exchange rates at stem, shoot, and forest floor levels were scaled up to the ecosystem
341 level (Fig. 1b). The values obtained are specific to the field conditions during the daytime
342 measurements in June 2019 only and should not be regarded as annual flux estimates. Beech
343 stems and shoots consumed a total of -1.07 ± 3.47 and $-249.9 \pm 84.3 \text{ mg N}_2\text{O ha}^{-1} \text{ ground area}$
344 h^{-1} , respectively, whereas the forest floor emitted $24.0 \pm 10.8 \text{ mg N}_2\text{O ha}^{-1} \text{ ground area h}^{-1}$. In
345 conclusion, the beech-dominated forest plot was estimated to be a strong net sink for N_2O (-227
346 $\text{mg ha}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$; i.e., sum of tree and forest floor fluxes at mean level). This is due to the substantial
347 contribution of beech shoots to the total N_2O fluxes, representing as much as 110.1% of the
348 estimated forest N_2O uptake (equal to 100%, Fig. 1b). Stem consumption contributed only 0.5%
349 to the forest N_2O uptake. The sole N_2O source was the forest floor, which reduced the forest
350 uptake by 10.6% (i.e., -10.6% contribution of forest floor, negative sign stands for different
351 flux direction – emission versus uptake).

352

353 4. Discussion

354 **4.1. Tree shoot N₂O fluxes**

355 Beech shoots were found to constitute a significant sink of N₂O from the atmosphere ($-4.54 \pm$
356 $1.53 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$). Measurements of N₂O fluxes from shoots of mature trees grown under
357 natural field conditions are unique worldwide, although leaves represent a significant surface
358 area for gas exchange within a forest. To our knowledge, there is only one study available on
359 leaf N₂O fluxes by mature trees from summer 2013, and it presents shoots of Scots pine trees
360 as predominantly weak emitters of N₂O ($0.097 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$; Machacova *et al.*, 2016). The
361 measured shoot CO₂ exchange was in agreement with other studies performed on mature beech
362 trees in the studied forest (e.g. Warren *et al.*, 2007).

363 The N₂O flux rates of the beech shoots showed a rather large variability, with a predominant
364 N₂O uptake but also with low N₂O emission. Higher flux variability during daytime also has
365 been found in pine trees, where needles predominantly emitted N₂O, but also consumed
366 atmospheric N₂O (Machacova *et al.*, 2016). Both studies were performed in a summer period
367 under daytime conditions. The observed variability could be closely related to rapidly changing
368 environmental conditions, especially light conditions, which affect the physiological activity of
369 trees, in particular photosynthetic, transpiration and sap flow rates and stomata opening regime.
370 The measured PAR values are only indicative (see 2. Methods) and could not be used for
371 detailed statistical analyses. Nevertheless, regression analysis revealed a weak relationship
372 between N₂O and CO₂ exchange of shoots ($R^2 = 0.145$, $p = 0.05$), with shoot CO₂ fluxes related
373 to the indicative PAR ($R^2 = 0.500$, $p < 0.001$). Simplified classification of shoot N₂O fluxes into
374 two groups according to leaf physiological activity (expressed by shoot CO₂ exchange)
375 confirmed this relationship. Terminal branches, characterized by high shoot CO₂ uptake during
376 the flux measurement period and mostly exposed to greater radiation, showed significantly
377 higher shoot N₂O uptake than did branches under lower PAR intensity and low shoot CO₂
378 exchange (Supporting Information Fig. S4). It appears, therefore, that shoot N₂O exchange is

379 at least partly dependent on light conditions and physiological activity of the tree. Ongoing
380 development of more sophisticated shoot chambers (e.g., Kohl *et al.*, 2021) will enable to study
381 these relationships in more detail in future.

382 The study shows that mature trees can exchange N₂O with the atmosphere through their leaves.
383 It also emphasizes the importance of measuring N₂O flux at the tree shoot level in field studies,
384 since this information was previously overlooked. The shoot N₂O exchange appears to be
385 related to tree physiological activity, showing high temporal flux variability. Therefore, future
386 studies should investigate the daily (including nighttime) and seasonal dynamics of N₂O fluxes,
387 the effects of tree physiology on the fluxes, and the spatial variability of the fluxes.

388

389 **4.2. Tree stem N₂O fluxes**

390 The investigation of trees' N₂O exchange potential is still a young research field. Under natural
391 field conditions, stems of different tree species, including both upland and wetland tree species,
392 mostly have been found to be low or even negligible N₂O emitters (Machacova *et al.*, 2016,
393 2017a, 2019; Schindler *et al.*, 2020, 2021; Mander *et al.*, 2021; Moldaschl *et al.*, 2021; Ranniku
394 *et al.*, 2023). First studies from the tropical zone show results similar to those from the colder
395 zones (Iddris *et al.*, 2020; Soosaar *et al.*, 2022).

396 Similarly, only low stem N₂O emissions were detected in young and mature European beech
397 trees grown under natural forest conditions ($< 6.3 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$, Díaz-Pinés *et al.*, 2016; 2.2
398 $\pm 0.31 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$, with peaks up to $4.7 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$, Wen *et al.* 2017). Moreover, even
399 a consistent uptake of atmospheric N₂O by mature beech stems was detected in two montane
400 beech forests in the Czech Republic and Germany under N₂O-consuming soil conditions
401 (Machacova *et al.*, 2017b). The montane beech trees showed even one order of magnitude
402 higher stem N₂O uptake rates (ranging between -2.4 and $-3.8 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$) compared to
403 the upland beech trees investigated in this study ($-0.254 \pm 0.827 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$). Besides

404 European beech trees, stems of various tree species growing in atypical tropical rainforests on
405 lava flows were identified as consistent N₂O sinks ($-3.0 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$; Machacova *et*
406 *al.*, 2021a), similar to the stem N₂O uptake of *Eperua falcata* ($-0.951 \pm 1.43 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$;
407 Bréchet *et al.*, 2021) and of other tropical tree species ($-31 \pm 32 \mu\text{g N m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$; Daniel *et al.*,
408 2023), both in French Guianese rainforests. Similar to the beech trees in our study, the adjacent
409 soils were characterized by very low soil N₂O fluxes (Machacova *et al.*, 2021a; Bréchet *et al.*,
410 2021).

411 The studied beech trees showed a vertical pattern of stem N₂O exchange. Only the lower parts
412 of the stems (0.2 m above ground) emitted N₂O, and the stems became N₂O sinks within the
413 first meter above ground. In montane beech trees, consistent N₂O uptake was detected already
414 at stem height of 0.4 m above ground and even in the buttress root area, and N₂O consumption
415 rates were uniform with respect to stem height above the soil (Machacova *et al.*, 2017b). Wen
416 *et al.* (2017) found no differences in beech stem N₂O fluxes with stem height, while Díaz-Pinés
417 *et al.* (2016) observed a decrease in beech stem N₂O emission rates with increasing stem height,
418 with fluxes below the detection limit at 2 m height. Vertical trends with increasing stem
419 measurement height for other tree species have shown different results, ranging from no trend
420 at all to a decrease (Moldaschl *et al.*, 2021) and a change from emission to consumption
421 (Mander *et al.*, 2021; Soosaar *et al.*, 2022). It is worth noting that most studies, including our
422 own, investigate N₂O fluxes from tree stems only in the first couple of meters above ground.

423 The stem N₂O fluxes of beech trees were not related to the stem CO₂ efflux, as was the case
424 for montane beech trees (Machacova *et al.*, 2017b) and boreal spruce, pine, and birch trees
425 (Machacova *et al.*, 2019). Thus, the hypothesis of physiologically dependent N₂O exchange in
426 tree stems (Machacova *et al.*, 2019) is not supported. Moreover, the stem N₂O fluxes appear to
427 be independent of soil N₂O concentrations. Even the tree growing in a hot spot for N₂O, where
428 soil N₂O concentrations reached up to 3.85 ppm N₂O at a depth of 40 cm, exhibited tree stem

429 N₂O fluxes similar to the other two studied trees growing under very low, sub-ambient soil N₂O
430 concentrations (0.13 – 0.17 ppm N₂O; Table 1). Therefore, it is possible that N₂O production
431 and/or consumption related to N₂O exchange by beech stems and shoots might predominantly
432 occur in tree tissues rather than in the soil (Smart & Bloom 2001; Hakata *et al.*, 2003).

433

434 **4.3. Unknown mechanisms of N₂O uptake by tree stems and shoots**

435 The ability of trees to take up N₂O from the atmosphere is a unique finding. The available
436 experimental results (this study; Bréchet *et al.*, 2021; Machacova *et al.*, 2021a; Daniel *et al.*,
437 2023) indicate that trees are able to exchange N₂O with the atmosphere in both directions under
438 certain environmental conditions. However, more in-depth investigations are urgently needed
439 to understand the still unknown mechanisms and processes involved in N₂O uptake by tree
440 stems and newly identified also by leaves and the unknown fate of the N₂O taken up.

441 First studies have shown that cryptogams growing on tree surfaces can emit N₂O to the
442 atmosphere (mostly studied under dark conditions; Lenhart *et al.*, 2015). However, incubation
443 of cryptogamic stem covers sampled from stems of European beech (Machacova *et al.*, 2017b)
444 and various tropical tree species (Machacova *et al.*, 2021a) under low light conditions of forest
445 understories identified these photoautotrophic organisms as consistent N₂O sinks. The N₂O
446 uptake rates of the studied lichens, mosses, and algae associated with tree stems were
447 comparable to the uptake rates of tree stems measured under natural field conditions
448 (Machacova *et al.*, 2017b, 2021a). The cryptogams may therefore also be responsible at least
449 in part for the unique uptake of N₂O by beech stems observed in this study. Some algae and/or
450 microorganisms involved in the N cycle could theoretically be present also on beech shoots and
451 thus potentially contribute to observed shoot N₂O uptake.

452 The processes behind N₂O uptake are still not explained. Mander *et al.* (2021) observed only
453 about 17% the volume of ecosystem N₂O emissions (measured by eddy-covariance) as that

454 calculated for soil N₂O emissions (100%) in a hemi-boreal riparian *Alnus incana* forest
455 ecosystem. The measured stem N₂O exchange was less than 1% of the cumulative soil fluxes
456 and could not explain the large difference (Mander *et al.*, 2021). Those authors hypothesized
457 UV-induced photodissociation of N₂O (see also Prather *et al.*, 2015 and Bao *et al.*, 2018) and
458 N₂O dissolution in atmospheric water. Based on the results of this study's first direct N₂O flux
459 measurements on tree leaves, the "consumption" of N₂O by the canopy observed by Mander *et*
460 *al.* (2021) could be explained by direct N₂O uptake by leaves. However, recently published
461 paper by Guerrieri *et al* (2024) demonstrates that intensive nitrification in forest canopies
462 produces nitrate which is likely washed down from canopies and possibly denitrified in soil.
463 Thus, this may decrease N₂O fluxes from canopies.

464 In conclusion, more detailed studies of N₂O uptake by tree stems and leaves, including
465 microbial analyses of plant material, are necessary to elucidate and describe the processes and
466 mechanisms responsible for N₂O uptake and the fate of "consumed" N₂O.

467

468 **4.4. Forest floor N₂O fluxes**

469 The floor of the beech forest was a predominantly weak source of N₂O to the atmosphere (2.41
470 $\pm 1.08 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$). The N₂O fluxes from the top soil were in the same order of magnitude,
471 independent of the highly variable N₂O concentrations detected in soil profiles close to the soil
472 chambers (ranging from sub-ambient up to 3.85 ppm N₂O concentrations, Table 1). Relatively
473 low soil water content and soil CO₂ concentrations barely above 1% indicated aerobic soil
474 conditions at all locations (Table 1).

475 The forest floor N₂O emission detected under the given daytime conditions in June 2019 seems
476 to be one of the lowest fluxes reported for European beech forests, when compared with caution
477 with other studies (short-term versus long-term character). As examples, Papen & Butterbach-
478 Bahl (1999) reported mean annual N₂O emissions of $184 \pm 7.2 \mu\text{g N}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$, Pihlatie *et al.*

479 (2005b) spring time N₂O emissions of 31 and 50 μg N₂O m⁻² h⁻¹ depending on the chamber
480 system used, Borken & Beese (2006) mean annual N₂O emissions of 50 μg N₂O m⁻² h⁻¹, and
481 Wen *et al.* (2017) vegetation season N₂O emissions of 9.1 ± 3.5 μg N₂O m⁻² h⁻¹. In contrast,
482 forest floors of two montane beech forests in the White Carpathians, Czech Republic, and the
483 Black Forest, Germany, were found to be sinks for N₂O in summer (-105 and -79 μg N₂O m⁻²
484 h⁻¹, respectively; Machacova *et al.*, 2017b).

485

486 **4.5. Beech forests as N₂O sink**

487 To allow comparison of N₂O flux rates between the studied forest compartments and rough
488 estimation of their contribution to the N₂O exchange of the beech-dominated forest plot, the
489 fluxes from tree stems and shoots and from the forest floor were scaled up to the ecosystem
490 level, although we are aware of the limitations of our study and the uncertainties associated
491 with the upscaling procedure, especially in the case of shoot fluxes. However, based on our
492 results, we dare to say that the common lack of canopy level N₂O fluxes in ecosystem flux
493 calculations for “safety” reasons may introduce substantial uncertainty in forest ecosystem N₂O
494 budget estimates. The beech stems and shoots absorbed -1.07 ± 3.47 and -249.9 ± 84.3 mg
495 N₂O ha⁻¹ h⁻¹ from the atmosphere, respectively, while the forest floor released 24.0 ± 10.8 mg
496 N₂O ha⁻¹ h⁻¹ into the atmosphere under the given daytime conditions in June 2019. Overall, the
497 European beech-dominated forest plot studied was estimated to be a strong net N₂O sink (-227
498 mg ha⁻¹ h⁻¹) at this period. Beech leaves, which had never been studied before under natural
499 field conditions, were substantial atmospheric N₂O sinks, dominating the total ecosystem N₂O
500 flux and contributing 110.1% to the estimated forest N₂O uptake during the daytime. The N₂O
501 uptake of stems was only 0.5% of the forest N₂O uptake. The N₂O emission from the forest
502 floor reduced the sink strength of the forest by 10.6% (Fig. 1). Despite the limitations, our study
503 clearly showed that the still common neglect of shoot fluxes in experiments may erroneously

504 bias the estimated direction of fluxes towards the N₂O source. Therefore, regardless the
505 technical, time and financial demands of the measurements in mature tree crowns, N₂O flux
506 measurements at the tree shoot level should be included in future field studies for correct
507 estimation of forest ecosystem N₂O budgets.

508

509 **5. Conclusion**

510 Our study highlights that not only the forest floor but also woody plants have the potential to
511 contribute significantly to N₂O exchange in forest ecosystems. To better understand greenhouse
512 gas flux dynamics and N cycle in forest ecosystems, it is necessary to include measurements of
513 the N₂O exchange potential of stems and leaves of woody plants in monitoring and
514 manipulation experiments. Leaves, which have not been extensively studied, may have a high
515 potential for N₂O exchange that has yet to be discovered and fully explored. This potential
516 should be investigated further in relation to various tree species in different forest ecosystems
517 and under a wide range of environmental conditions. Flux measurements under different light
518 conditions (day-night) and detailed microbial analyses of stem and leaf tissues, while including
519 also associated cryptogams, would help to understand the still unknown mechanisms and
520 processes behind N₂O uptake.

521

522 **Acknowledgements**

523 This research was supported by the Czech Science Foundation [17-18112Y]; project SustES -
524 Adaptation strategies for sustainable ecosystem services and food security under adverse
525 environmental conditions [CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/16_019/0000797]; project AdAgriF - Advanced
526 methods of greenhouse gases emission reduction and sequestration in agriculture and forest
527 landscape for climate change mitigation [CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004635]; the Ministry of

528 Education, Youth and Sports of CR within the CzeCOS program [grant number LM2023048];
529 and the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of CR within the LU - INTER-EXCELLENCE
530 II (2022 - 2029) program [grant number LUC23162]. This study was also supported by the
531 Estonian Research Council [grants PRG352 and MOBERC44] and by the EU through the
532 European Regional Development Fund [Centre of Excellence EcolChange]. We thank Jan
533 Hrdlička and Thomas Feuerbach for their technical support and Kateřina Svobodová for the gas
534 chromatographic analyses.

535

536 **Declaration of competing interest**

537 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
538 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

539

540 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

541 Katerina Machacova: Conceptualization, Field work, Data processing, Funding and
542 administrative management, Writing - Original draft preparation; Thomas Schindler:
543 Conceptualization, Field work, Data processing, Writing - review & editing; Laëtitia Bréchet:
544 Writing - review & editing; Ůlo Mander: Writing - review & editing; Thorsten E. E. Grams:
545 Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing.

546

547 **Data Availability**

548 The datasets generated and analysed during this study are available from the authors upon
549 reasonable request.

550

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698 **Appendix A. Supplementary data** (single sentence legend for each item)

699 **Fig. S1** View of the field experimental set-up.

700 **Fig. S2** Carbon dioxide (CO₂) fluxes in forest floor, tree stems, and tree shoots of European
701 beech.

702 **Fig. S3** Fluxes of carbon dioxide (CO₂) from stem vertical profiles of European beech.

703 **Fig. S4** Fluxes of nitrous oxide (N₂O) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) from shoots of European beech
704 under high and low shoot CO₂ uptake.

705 **Note S1** Quality check of N₂O signal in shoot flux measurements with portable Fourier
706 transform infrared spectroscopy gas analyser.

707 **Tables**

708 **Table 1 Soil parameters.** Vertical soil profiles of nitrous oxide (N₂O) and carbon dioxide
 709 (CO₂) concentrations, soil volumetric water content (VWC), and soil temperature (at 10 cm soil
 710 depth) were determined simultaneously with forest floor gas flux measurements at each soil
 711 position. Mean values (\pm standard error) from three soil positions are presented, except for N₂O
 712 concentrations, where soil near soil chamber 1 exhibited high N₂O concentrations (i.e., N₂O
 713 conc.^a), whereas soil adjacent to soil chambers 2 and 3 showed similarly low N₂O
 714 concentrations (i.e., N₂O conc.^b).

	N ₂ O conc. ^a	N ₂ O conc. ^b	CO ₂ conc.	VWC	Temp.
Soil depth	(ppm)	(ppm)	(ppm)	(m ³ m ⁻³)	(°C)
10 cm	1.803 \pm 0.112	0.164 \pm 0.009	6935 \pm 553	0.246 \pm 0.014	14.7 \pm 0.16
20 cm	2.858 \pm 0.293	0.130 \pm 0.010	8320 \pm 588	0.184 \pm 0.011	-
30 cm	2.258 \pm 0.341	0.133 \pm 0.013	7831 \pm 675	0.253 \pm 0.021	-
40 cm	3.847 \pm 0.398	0.165 \pm 0.013	9513 \pm 647	0.359 \pm 0.004	-

715 *“a” is standing for N₂O concentrations at four soil depths of the soil position 1. “b” is*
 716 *standing for mean N₂O concentrations in soil profile at soil positions 2 and 3.*

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720

721 **Fig. 1** Nitrous oxide (N₂O) fluxes in forest floor, tree stems, and tree shoots of European beech.

722 Fluxes are expressed per unit of soil, stem, or leaf surface area (a) and scaled up to unit ground

723 area of temperate forest (b). Fluxes are expressed as medians (solid line) and means (broken

724 line) of repeated measurements at three soil positions and three beech trees. Box boundaries

725 indicate 25th and 75th percentile boundaries. Whiskers indicate 10th and 90th percentiles. Dots

726 mark outliers. Positive fluxes indicate trace gas emission and negative fluxes trace gas uptake.

727 Statistically significant differences at $p < 0.05$ (Kruskal–Wallis one-way ANOVA on ranks)

728 between the scaled-up fluxes at forest floor, tree stem, and tree shoot levels are indicated by

729 different letters above the bars. Contributions of forest floor, tree stem, and tree shoot fluxes to

730 total N₂O flux (i.e., sum of these fluxes at the mean level, $-227 \text{ mg ha}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$, equal to 100%) are

731 expressed as percentages of the total flux.

732

733

734 **Fig. 2** Fluxes of nitrous oxide (N₂O) from stem vertical profiles of European beech (*n* = 3, 4
 735 measurement sets). Measurements were made at three stem heights of ca 0.2, 0.9, and 1.8 m
 736 above ground. All fluxes are expressed as medians (solid lines) and means (broken lines) of the
 737 measurements and are related to m² of stem area. Box boundaries represent 25th and 75th
 738 percentiles and whiskers 10th and 90th percentiles. Dots mark outliers. Positive fluxes indicate
 739 trace gas emission and negative fluxes indicate trace gas uptake. Statistically significant
 740 differences between fluxes of different heights at *p* < 0.05 (Kruskal–Wallis one-way ANOVA
 741 on ranks) are indicated by different letters above the bars.

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